

Hodo Abubakar

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The Politics of the ‘Whole Person’: Identity Essays and Institutional Power in College Admissions

Prompt: Some students have a background, identity, interest, or talent that is so meaningful they believe their application would be incomplete without it. If this sounds like you, then please share your story.

This question is designed to get to know the applicant on a deeper level and to understand what makes them unique. Certain colleges are interested in knowing more about the applicant’s personal experiences, values, and perspectives, which can help create a diverse and well-rounded student body. The student will demonstrate their strengths, abilities, and personal qualities, which can help the admission officers to determine if the student is a good fit for the institution. This question supports the applicant in showcasing their personality, character, and writing skills. I will analyze how this prompt effectively communicates higher education functions, purposes, systems, institutional types, and stakeholders with respect to the assigned readings.

With this prompt in mind, the function of a college seems more personalized with a strong sense of individuality because the applicant is given the space to share their story. As discussed in the *Sieve, Incubator, Temple, and Hub* paper, colleges focus not only on academic progress but also on character growth. This character growth is described by Mitchell L Steven and his two other co-authors as probity and stamina, which is basically striving for the betterment of their virtue. This growth cannot be done in a setting where everyone has the same experiences and skills, that is where lateral learning comes in. Lateral learning or learning from

others is not only beneficial for collective growth but it is also a way of eliminating preconceived notions of specific backgrounds and identities. Therefore, this prompt conveys the function of an institution because it measures the stage of someone's character and if they can teach their peers something of their non-academic knowledge.

In addition, the prompt captures the purposes of college by capturing the characteristics they care about such as background, identity, interests, and talents. It does not mean that they will admit anyone with talent, but it gives them the opportunity to pick out the ones that seem fit for their institution. This is what Selingo was talking about: colleges' transparency in the attributes they are looking for in an applicant. This transparency benefits both the institution and the applicant because it gives the institution the power of obscurity, which helps them to be consistent despite their changing preferences. It benefits the applicant as well because no one is perfect and has the perfect score in all the categories from extracurricular activities, academics, sports, etc. Therefore, it is in the favor of both parties to consider the "whole person" in the college application process.

Despite how individualistic the process of admission might seem; the purpose of a college is to shape the views of the admitted group. One of the examples Delbanco provides is to change the perspective of oneself and implement a broader view of life through constant self-reflection in the light of new experiences. Delbanco makes the argument that going to college is an exercise of self-discipline and self-examination. There is a huge emphasis on the self, however, it does not mean that self-development and the collective goal are discrete units. He is just saying that everyone is striving towards the same goal using the same individual practices. All individuals are engaged in self-discipline and self-examination even though they are doing it individually. Consequently, this prompt supports the purpose of a college because the

shared individual stories are looked at as a part of the whole to produce a well-informed generation.

Along with the functions and purposes of a college, the prompt represents the system of colleges. David Labaree describes the American system of higher education as democratic and extraordinarily hierarchical because of the way the system rose from the bottom up, out of the competition among colleges for students. Thus, this prompt compliments the idea that the system is defended against charges of unfairness because of its ability to create a situation where the system gets credit for openness and the student bears the burden of failing to take advantage of it. For example, in Paul Tough's piece, he shared the story of Shannen and how hard she worked throughout high school and had the perfect GPA but still got rejected by Penn. Shannen was miserable because that is not what her family or friends expected from her even though she knows she gave it her best. This is what Labaree meant about the system being open and applicants failing to capitalize on the opportunity. Thus, the broadness of this prompt speaks to the double standards in the system.

Finally what institution types does this prompt fit and what interests are they trying to get out of this question? This prompt is a good fit for elite/ liberal arts colleges and universities but not a fit for community/public institutions or online institutions. According to Arthur M Cohen and Florence B Brawer, community colleges let you go back and pick up classes to gain new skills. They are not tied to the credential of the college because they are about learning developmental education. Similarly online and for-profit institutions care about the number of applicants more than their qualifications so they would not care about an applicant's story (unless it is for commercial reasons). Tressie Cottom states that online and for-profit institutions are trying to attract lower-income students and non-traditional students, so they do not want to scare

them with essay questions. On the other hand, liberal arts institutions are looking for well-rounded students and research scientists and they are trying to teach something of everything. So, it makes sense that they want to know who is part of their community and what they bring to the table.

In addition, Labaree mentions that institutions are interested in what advantages applicants bring to them such as culture, capital, connection, and family wealth. It is impractical to put a score to these advantages so this prompt functions as a window to these advantages that cannot be bluntly stated in the application. For example, this prompt can be used to look at the demographics of the applicant and the hardships they have overcome, the bigger picture. As a result, this essay prompt matches the mission of elite and liberal arts colleges and universities in helping them understand who is part of their community and the prompt enables them to collect that information with the consent of their applicants.

Ultimately, this prompt complements the mission of liberal and elite colleges because it supports the institution system and its functions and purposes. It fulfills this by disguising the specific requirements that these institutions are looking for in applicants. However, it also creates the space for all applicants to share their stories and convince the admissions that they belong in the institutions they apply to. These stories not only show the student's efforts in pursuing education, but they provide colleges with the information they could use to shape the graduate class they want. Since knowledge is power, this prompt empowers the institutions more than the applicant.

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